

Online Survey for DMP-Guidance from Research Data Alliance Working Group *Discipline-specific Guidance for DMP*

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Introduction text

Purpose of this survey

The purpose of this survey is to understand the current state of discipline-specific DMPs and data (and code) management practices among the international research community. By research data, the [RDA WG Discipline-Specific Guidance for DMPs](#) means any information which supports research findings (for example, laboratory observations and measurements, interviews, code, spreadsheets, videos, images, protocols and other types of data).

Use of information you provide

To ensure transparency in our methodology and findings, and to maximise the re-use potential of any information acquired, anonymised data resulting from this survey will be shared publicly. To protect the anonymity of study participants, answers to the open question(s) will be only presented in aggregated analyses.

By filling in this survey you acknowledge that you have understood, and agreed to public sharing of anonymised data resulting from this survey.

At the end of the survey, you will be asked if you would like to provide further contact information to stay in touch and be invited for an interview or discussion group wherein we will gather more specific expertise and knowledge. If you agree to provide your contact information, you will be redirected to a separate survey that is not linked to the current one. Providing your contact information is entirely optional.

All of the answers you will provide in both surveys will be stored securely on a server in Europe. It will not be possible beyond the RDA and RDA Discipline-Specific Guidance for DMPs (Data Management Plans) Working Group to identify you as an individual. For more information, please see the [RDA general privacy policy](#).

Survey Sections

Demographics

1. Which position do you have?
 - Professor (assistant/ associate/ full)
 - PostDoc/ Senior Researcher
 - PhD Candidate
 - Research Support
 - Other, specifically _____
 - Student
 - Research Technician
 - Researcher
 - Research Support
2. Discipline (**You may work in or support more than one discipline; please choose the one where you spend the majority of your time**)* (DFG classification)
 - Humanities and Social Sciences
 - Life Sciences
 - Natural sciences
 - Engineering sciences
 - Other, (with pre-defined options based on existing discipline standards)
3. Where are you from?

Data Description and Collection

For this survey, research data are defined as factual records (numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds) used as primary sources for scientific research, and that are commonly accepted in the scientific community as necessary to validate research findings. A research data set constitutes a systematic, partial representation of the subject being investigated. However, not everyone calls these sources “data”.

4. What kind of research data do you use or are used in the domains you support?

multiple responses possible

- Tabular data
- Textual data (such as interview transcripts or survey responses)
- References (i.e. bibliography)
- Binary or numerical data
- Big data (heterological data types)
- Audio recordings
- Visual recordings
- Audiovisual recordings
- Images
- 3D models
- Algorithms
- Simulations
- Code/software
- Paper or digital documentation
- Physical samples, including: _____
- Other, namely: _____

NOTE: For the sake of simplicity, the sources of information used in your research will be referred to as "data" for the remainder of the questionnaire

5. How do you or the researchers you support produce or collect data for analysis?

multiple responses possible

- Via observations (by human observation, instruments, or sensors)
- Via surveys
- Via interviews
- Via lab experiments
- Via social science experiments
- Via field experiments
- Via derivation or compilation from other data sources
- Via computations, models or simulations
- Via bibliographies
- Via catalogues, repositories, or databases
- Via crowdsourcing
- Via web scraping
- Other, namely: _____

6. Do you or the researchers you support ever re-use existing data?
- Yes, pre-existing data that has been published is used, such as _____
 - Yes, pre-existing data that was created/collected by me or my reserach group is reused, such as _____
 - No, pre-existing data is not used, because: _____
 - There are no pre-existing data relevant to the discipline
 - Pre-existing data are not used due to privacy (personal data) or other types of confidentiality concerns (intellectual property rights, national security...)
 - Pre-existing data are not used due to insufficient documentation on how to reuse the data
 - I do not know

Data Documentation & Quality

7. Do you or the researchers you support describe data with metadata?
Metadata is "data about data"; it provides information about the data. For example, information such as location and date about sample collection are metadata about the sample.
- Yes, data is described with metadata like: _____
 - No, metadata are not used, because: _____
 - Don't know how to use any metadata
8. What documentation do you or the researchers you support generate about data so that the data are interpretable, replicable and/or reproducible?**multiple responses possible**
- Codebooks
 - Notebooks
 - Readme files
 - Use of naming conventions
 - (Electronic) lab notebooks/logbooks
 - Field notes
 - Documentation of the used or created hardware/equipment
 - Documentation of the used or created software

9. Do you or the researchers you support write code and/or develop software? If so, how do you or the researchers you support make it understandable and reusable? **multiple responses possible**

Software could be written code or i.e. statistical software in the processing and analysis of data like R or MATLAB. Practical steps could be a.k.a. scripts or syntaxes or any standard like use of white space, writing comments, etc..

- I or the researchers I support do not write code or develop software
- I or the researchers I support write code and/or develop software, but don't know of any best practices
- I or the researchers I support comment in code
- I or the researchers I support make scripts publicly available
- Yes, I or the researchers I support use version control to manage code
- Other

10. Do you or the researchers you support use file naming conventions for naming data files? **multiple responses possible**

- Yes, file naming conventions based on a local, standard convention are used, specifically: _____
- Yes, pre-planned conventions are not used, but ad hoc naming conventions are built during file creation, for example: _____
- No, file naming conventions are not used
- I don't know

11. How is the quality of data controlled?

- With a calibration method
- With repeated samples or measurements
- With a standardised data capture
- With a data entry validation
- With peer reviewed data
- With controlled vocabulary
- Other, namely: _____

Data Archiving, Publishing & Sharing After the Project

12. Which data/code do you or the researchers you support keep for the long-term (at least 10 years) after the project? **multiple responses possible**

- All raw data from the project
- All processed data from the project
- All final versions of processed data from the project
- Raw data underlying published articles
- Processed data underlying published articles
- Final versions of processed data underlying published articles
- All own code/software developed for data processing/analysis for the project
- All own code/software developed for computations, models or simulations for the project
- Own code/software developed for data processing/analysis underlying published articles
- Own code/software developed for computations, models or simulations underlying published articles
- No data/code at all

13. Do you or the researchers you support publicly/openly share data/code for the long-term (at least 10 years) after the project? **multiple responses possible**

- Yes, data are shared data via a disciplinary platform/repository named as _____.
- Yes, data are shared via an institutional platform/repository named as _____.
- Yes, code is shared via a code hosting platform (GitHub, GitLab, Bitbucket, Subversion (SVN) etc.) named as _____.
- Yes, data/code is shared via a generalist platform/repository (Zenodo, figshare, Dryad, OSF etc.) named as _____.
- Yes, data/ code are shared under the supplementary data/materials section of corresponding papers
- Yes, data/ code are shared via a commercial provider like Google Drive, Dropbox,
- Yes, data/ code are shared via personal/lab/department website or server
- Yes, data are shared via another way by _____.
- Yes, code are shared via another way by _____.
- No, data/code are not publicly shared because _____.

14. Where do you or the researchers you support keep the data/code that are not publicly/openly shared in the long term (at least 10 years) after the project? **multiple responses possible**

- Data/code are kept on PC/laptops.
- Data/code are kept on external hard drives.
- Data/code are kept on USB sticks.
- Data/code are kept on cloud storage.
- Data/code are kept with closed/restricted access on a disciplinary platform/repository named _____.
- Data/code are kept with closed/restricted access on an institutional platform/repository named as _____.
- Data/code are kept with closed/restricted access on a generalist platform/repository (Zenodo, Dryad, OSF etc.) named as _____.
- The code is kept in a private repository on a code hosting platform (GitHub, GitLab, Bitbucket etc.)
- The data/code are kept in another storage location named as _____.
- No data/code are kept in the long term after the project because _____.
- Not applicable, all the data/code are publicly/openly shared.

15. Do you or the researchers you support use Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to make published work easily findable? If so, what type ? **multiple responses possible**

- No, there isn't any persistent identifier associated with corresponding published work
- Yes, HS - Handle system
- Yes, DOI - Digital Object Identifier
- Yes, PURL - Persistent Universal Resource Locator
- Yes, URN - Uniform Resource name, like ISBN (international standard book number)
- Yes, ARK - Archival Resource Key
- Yes, DAI - Digital Author Identifier (for yourself or fellow authors)
- Yes, XRI - Extensible Resource Identifiers
- Yes, Others like _____
- I am not sure what a persistent identifier is

16. Do you or the researchers you support apply licences to the data/code? **multiple responses possible**

- I don't know what licenses are
- Not applicable, nothing is shared/published
- No, licences are not used when sharing or publishing data/code etc.
- Yes, CC0 (data)
- Yes, CC-BY (data)
- Yes, CC-BY-NC (data)
- Yes, CC-BY-SA (data)
- Yes, CC-BY-NC-SA (data)
- Yes, MIT license (code)
- Yes, Apache (code)
- Yes, GNU (code)
- Yes, BSD (code)
- Yes, GPL (code)
- Yes, Proprietary licensing (specific agreements have to be made for code, data)
- Yes, Commercial licenses, available for purchase (books, compendiums etc)
- Yes, other(s) namely _____

Guidelines, Principles & Best Practices

17. Do you or the researchers you support make use of any guidelines for research data management? **multiple responses possible**

- Yes, the following **discipline-specific** guidelines are used: _____
- Yes, the following guidelines from my **institution** are used: _____
- Yes, the following **general** guidelines are used: _____
- I don't know of any guidelines for research data management
- No, guidelines for research data management are not used because: _____

18. Are there learning resources about research data management available to you or the researchers you support? **multiple responses possible**

- Yes, the following **discipline-specific** learning resource(s) is available:

- Yes, the following **institutional** learning resource(s) is available: _____
- Yes, the following **general** learning resource(s) is available: _____
- No, there are not any learning resources on research data management available.

19. Are there any legal, ethical or contractual obligations that impact how you or the researchers you support carry out research data management?

Legal: compliance with regulations about personal data such as GDPR, HIPAA ...

Ethical: risks/considerations for instance for research including human participants, animals ...

Contractual: specific conditions in consortium agreement, non-disclosure agreement, ...

multiple responses possible

- Yes, there are obligations to meet the following **legal** obligations: _____
- Yes, there are obligations to meet the following **ethical** obligations: _____
- Yes, there are obligations to meet the following **contractual** obligations:

- No, there are no obligations that impact research data management in my discipline that I am aware of

20. Have you or the researchers you support attempted to apply the FAIR-principles to your research data management practices? **multiple responses possible**

- Yes, the FAIR-principles are partly applied throughout the research process, but it is still a work in progress because: _____
- No, it has not been possible to apply the FAIR-principles at all because:

21. Do you or the researchers you support use any metadata standards or standard terminologies in your research?

A standard could be a word list - words or phrases that are common in your discipline and can get more complex up to an ontology - words or phrases are put in relation to each other like <https://physh.aps.org/>.

- Yes, general metadata standards are used: _____
- Yes, discipline-specific metadata standard are used: _____
- Yes, the following standard terminologies are used: _____
- I don't know what metadata standards are
- I don't know what standard terminologies are
- No, metadata standards or standard terminologies are not used because:

Follow-up interviews and group discussions

22. Would you be interested in participating in interviews or group discussions, wherein we can learn more about your specific discipline's needs and gather more of your specific expertise and knowledge on this topic? If you are interested, select "Yes" and you will be directed to a separate questionnaire that is not linked to the current one.

Yes

No

Last Page

Thank you for your participation!

We would like to sincerely thank you for your assistance with the Discipline-Specific Catalog for Data Management Plans. The data as well as the catalog will be made available on the [RDA WG website](#) as well as on Zenodo in the RDA related documents community.

If you have any general or personal questions, please do not hesitate to contact us.

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If you would like to leave any questions, comments or suggestions, please feel free to fill them in below:

[Open text field]

SEPARATE SURVEY FOR CONTACT INFORMATION

Thank you for agreeing to provide your contact information to be contacted for follow-up interviews or focus groups.

Name: [Open text field]*

Role: [Open text field]

Affiliation: [Open text field]

E-mail address: [Open text field]*

*Required fields